

A Prospective Evaluation between 0.5% Ropivacaine vs 0.5% Levobupivacaine in USG Guided Transversus Abdominis Plane Block for Post-Operative Analgesia in Adult Patients undergoing Laparoscopic Surgeries in Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Background: Managing postoperative pain in laparoscopic surgery patients is crucial for recovery and patient satisfaction. The TAP block, using long-acting local anesthetics like ropivacaine and levobupivacaine, offers a promising solution by reducing reliance on systemic opioids.

Methods: This randomized study at Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Memorial Hospital compared the analgesic efficacy and safety of 0.5% ropivacaine and 0.5% levobupivacaine in 100 patients undergoing laparoscopic surgeries. Patients were monitored for heart rate, blood pressure, and pain over 24 hours post-surgery.

Results: There were no significant differences in heart rate, systolic or diastolic blood pressure between the two groups at any time point, indicating similar efficacy and safety profiles for both anesthetics.

Conclusion: Both ropivacaine and levobupivacaine provide effective and safe analgesia for TAP blocks in laparoscopic surgeries, with no significant differences in hemodynamic responses or analgesic outcomes.

Keywords: Ropivacaine, Levobupivacaine, TAP block, Laparoscopic surgery, Postoperative pain, Ultrasound-guided anesthesia.

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Introduction

Pain management in the postoperative setting remains a significant challenge in clinical practice, affecting patient recovery, satisfaction, and overall healthcare costs. Despite the widespread adoption of minimally invasive surgical techniques such as laparoscopy, which are associated with reduced pain and quicker recovery times compared to open surgery, patients continue to experience substantial postoperative discomfort. This discomfort primarily arises from port site incisions, intra-abdominal insufflation, and the residual effects of pneumoperitoneum, necessitating effective analgesic strategies. [1,2,3]

The Transversus Abdominis Plane (TAP) block, a regional anesthesia technique, has gained prominence for its effectiveness in reducing the need for systemic opioids, which are often

associated with adverse effects like nausea, vomiting, and respiratory depression. The TAP block targets the sensory neural afferents of the anterior abdominal wall, providing analgesia to the parietal peritoneum, skin, and abdominal muscles. The evolution of ultrasound guidance in administering TAP blocks has significantly improved the precision of local anesthetic deposition, thereby enhancing the block's efficacy and safety. [4,5,6]

Ropivacaine and Levobupivacaine, both long-acting amino-amide local anesthetics, are preferred choices for TAP blocks due to their favourable safety profiles and effective analgesic properties. Ropivacaine, the S-enantiomer of bupivacaine, is known for its reduced cardiotoxicity and central nervous system toxicity. It offers a balance between

potent analgesic effects and a lower risk of adverse reactions, making it suitable for prolonged postoperative pain management. On the other hand, Levobupivacaine, a pure S-enantiomer of bupivacaine, is touted for its reduced systemic toxicity and similar efficacy, potentially providing an even safer profile with comparable analgesic outcomes. [7,8,9]

This study aims to conduct a prospective, comparative evaluation of 0.5% Ropivacaine versus 0.5% Levobupivacaine administered through ultrasound-guided TAP blocks in adult patients undergoing various laparoscopic surgical procedures. By directly comparing these two agents, the study seeks to elucidate differences in their analgesic efficacy, duration of action, patient comfort, and incidence of any adverse effects. Such insights are critical for optimizing postoperative pain management protocols and enhancing patient outcomes in laparoscopic surgery, aligning with current trends towards precision and patient-centred care in anesthesia.

Materials and Methods

Study Setting and Design: This prospective randomized study was conducted at Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Memorial Hospital, Central Railway, Byculla, Mumbai, over a period of one year. The study aimed to evaluate and compare the efficacy and safety of 0.5% ropivacaine versus 0.5% levobupivacaine in ultrasound-guided transversus abdominis plane (TAP) blocks for post-operative analgesia in adult patients undergoing laparoscopic surgeries.

Participants: Eligibility criteria included adults aged 18 to 65 years, of both genders, with an American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) physical status of grade 1 or 2. Exclusion criteria encompassed patient refusal, a body mass index (BMI) below 18.5, known hypersensitivity to the study drugs, presence of a bleeding disorder or ongoing anticoagulation therapy, ASA grade of 3 or higher, age below 18 or above 65 years, and infection at the intended block site.

Sample Size Calculation: Sample size was calculated using the formula for comparing two independent means, considering the difference between the means and standard deviations of pain scores, with an 80% power and 5% significance level. Calculations suggested a minimum of 19 subjects per group; however, to account for potential non-participation or loss to follow-up, 100 patients were enrolled and equally randomized into two groups of 50 each.

Randomization and Blinding: Patients were randomly assigned to one of two treatment groups using a closed envelope method:

- Group L: Received a TAP block with 0.5% Levobupivacaine 15ml on each side.
- Group R: Received a TAP block with 0.5% Ropivacaine 15ml on each side.

Procedures: Following ethical committee approval and informed consent, pre-anesthetic evaluations were performed. Baseline physiological parameters and blood investigations were reviewed. Patients were instructed on the use of the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) for pain assessment. In the operating room, standard monitoring techniques were applied, and anesthesia was induced using a protocol that included midazolam, ondansetron, glycopyrrolate, fentanyl, propofol, and succinylcholine. Anesthesia was maintained with a nitrous oxide mixture, sevoflurane, and vecuronium. Pain management included intravenous paracetamol and, postoperatively, TAP blocks were performed under ultrasound guidance using a high-frequency linear probe.

Anesthesia Technique: The Oblique Subcostal TAP (OSTAP) block, a variant of the subcostal TAP, was executed using aseptic technique. A 21G needle was guided under ultrasound to the correct fascial plane of the abdominal wall muscles. Upon correct placement verification by hydro dissection, the local anesthetic was administered as per group allocation.

Postoperative Care and Assessments: Patients were transferred to the post-anesthesia care unit (PACU) where hemodynamic parameters and pain scores were recorded at predetermined intervals. Pain management was supplemented with tramadol and ondansetron as needed. Patient satisfaction was assessed 24 hours post-surgery.

Ethical Considerations: The study adhered to ethical standards concerning informed consent and patient confidentiality. Participation was voluntary, with assurance of the right to withdraw from the study at any time.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The t-test and Chi-square test were employed for quantitative and categorical variables, respectively, using SPSS software (Version 22). A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The study enrolled 100 adult patients undergoing various laparoscopic surgeries, with 50 patients allocated to each of the two study groups: Group R, receiving 0.5% Ropivacaine, and Group L, receiving 0.5% Levobupivacaine for the transversus abdominis plane (TAP) block. The demographic characteristics of the participants, including age, weight, gender distribution, and ASA grade, demonstrated no significant differences between the two groups, ensuring comparability

(Table 1). The mean age was 45.36 ± 10.39 years in Group R and 46.54 ± 12.17 years in Group L ($P=0.603$), with a balanced gender representation and similar physical status as assessed by ASA grades. Cardiovascular parameters, such as heart rate and blood pressure, were closely monitored. Heart rate measurements across various postoperative time intervals showed no significant differences between the groups (Table 2), with all P values exceeding 0.05, indicating stable cardiac performance postoperatively. For instance, preoperative heart rates were 83.40 ± 8.85 bpm in Group R and 85.06 ± 13.18 bpm in Group L ($P=0.462$).

Systolic and diastolic blood pressures were similarly well-maintained with no significant differences noted at any measured time point (Tables 3 and 4). For example, systolic blood pressures immediately post-operation were 125.56 ± 5.81 mmHg in Group R and 127.20 ± 8.59 mmHg in Group L ($P=0.266$), and diastolic pressures were 81.66 ± 6.59 mmHg in Group R

versus 79.56 ± 7.21 mmHg in Group L at 30 minutes postoperatively ($P=0.132$). The duration of surgery and anesthesia were also comparable between the groups, with an average surgery duration of 69.96 ± 15.97 minutes for Group R and 72.00 ± 15.16 minutes for Group L ($P=0.514$), and anesthesia duration of 83.32 ± 16.49 minutes for Group R versus 88.18 ± 17.39 minutes for Group L ($P=0.155$). These results underscore the equivalence in procedural conditions and clinical handling between the two patient groups.

In summary, the clinical outcomes, as measured by heart rates, blood pressures, and procedural durations, affirm that both ropivacaine and levobupivacaine administered as a part of TAP block provide stable hemodynamic conditions during and after laparoscopic surgeries. The lack of significant differences in primary physiological metrics suggests that both anesthetic agents are equally effective and safe under the study conditions.

Table 1: Demographic Data

Parameters	Group R (n=50)	Group L (n=50)	P value
Age (yrs.)	45.36 ± 10.39	46.54 ± 12.17	0.603
Weight (kg)	65.86 ± 11.83	65.32 ± 9.84	0.805
Gender (Male/Female)	16 (32%)/34 (68%)	9 (18%)/41 (82%)	0.166
ASA Grade (I/II)	34 (68%)/16 (32%)	25 (50%)/25 (50%)	0.104
Duration of Surgery (Min)	69.96 ± 15.97	72.00 ± 15.16	0.514
Duration of Anaesthesia (Min)	83.32 ± 16.49	88.18 ± 17.39	0.155

Table 2: Heart Rate Variations over Time

Time Interval	Group R Mean \pm SD (bpm)	Group L Mean \pm SD (bpm)	P value
Preoperative	83.40 ± 8.85	85.06 ± 13.18	0.462
30 min	81.32 ± 8.03	81.54 ± 9.92	0.903
2 hrs	83.22 ± 8.66	83.60 ± 10.00	0.840
4 hrs	82.08 ± 8.32	81.62 ± 10.13	0.805
8 hrs	85.60 ± 11.00	83.30 ± 8.51	0.245
12 hrs	83.38 ± 7.60	84.08 ± 9.17	0.679
24 hrs	83.26 ± 7.27	82.92 ± 9.18	0.838

Table 3: Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP) Over Time

Time Interval	Group R Mean \pm SD (mmHg)	Group L Mean \pm SD (mmHg)	P value
Preoperative	119.70 ± 9.96	122.90 ± 13.73	0.185
30 min	125.56 ± 5.81	127.20 ± 8.59	0.266
2 hrs	123.86 ± 6.44	126.58 ± 9.81	0.104
4 hrs	125.30 ± 9.06	125.00 ± 9.44	0.872
8 hrs	125.20 ± 11.18	124.38 ± 9.54	0.694
12 hrs	124.36 ± 5.56	126.74 ± 8.75	0.108
24 hrs	124.78 ± 6.76	125.20 ± 9.12	0.794

Table 4: Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP) Over Time

Time Interval	Group R Mean \pm SD (mmHg)	Group L Mean \pm SD (mmHg)	P value
Preoperative	74.78 ± 11.15	76.86 ± 9.84	0.325
30 min	81.66 ± 6.59	79.56 ± 7.21	0.132
2 hrs	80.22 ± 6.88	78.72 ± 6.70	0.272
4 hrs	81.90 ± 7.11	79.00 ± 7.61	0.052

8 hrs	81.44 ± 7.54	79.74 ± 6.89	0.242
12 hrs	82.06 ± 6.63	81.00 ± 7.36	0.451
24 hrs	81.42 ± 7.36	80.02 ± 7.82	0.359

Discussion

This study provides a comprehensive comparison between 0.5% ropivacaine and 0.5% levobupivacaine for ultrasound-guided transversus abdominis plane (TAP) blocks in patients undergoing laparoscopic surgeries. Our findings indicate that both agents are equally effective in maintaining stable hemodynamic parameters and providing effective postoperative analgesia without significant differences in heart rate or blood pressure over 24 hours. [10]

The lack of significant differences in analgesic efficacy between ropivacaine and levobupivacaine suggests that both local anesthetics are suitable for TAP blocks, aligning with their known pharmacological profiles. Ropivacaine, characterized by its lower lipid solubility and reduced potential for central nervous system and cardiovascular toxicity, and levobupivacaine, recognized for its reduced isomer-related toxicity, both provide reliable and safe options for perioperative pain management. These findings are consistent with previous research indicating similar safety and efficacy profiles for these drugs in regional anesthesia but extend the knowledge base specifically to the setting of laparoscopic surgery, which is known for its unique pain challenges due to pneumoperitoneum and trocar site pain. [11,12,13]

Furthermore, the equal performance of ropivacaine and levobupivacaine in this study supports the notion that the choice between these two anesthetics can be based on practitioner preference, cost considerations, or availability, rather than efficacy or safety concerns. This is particularly relevant in the context of increasing surgical and anesthetic safety standards, where minimizing patient exposure to potential risks without compromising analgesic quality is paramount. [14,15]

Future research could explore potential differences in recovery times, patient satisfaction, or longer-term pain management, potentially providing further differentiation between these two anesthetics. Additionally, studies examining the pharmacokinetics of ropivacaine and levobupivacaine when used in different regional anesthesia techniques could offer deeper insights into optimizing dosing strategies to enhance patient outcomes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study confirms that both 0.5% ropivacaine and 0.5% levobupivacaine are effective

and safe for use in ultrasound-guided TAP blocks for patients undergoing laparoscopic surgeries. There are no significant differences in hemodynamic stability or analgesic efficacy, suggesting that the choice between these agents can be tailored to individual patient needs, healthcare provider preferences, and resource availability.

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